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STRUCTURE FORMATION OF PORTLAND CEMENT MODIFIED WITH
METALLURGICAL PRODUCTION WASTE

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Abstract: This paper presents the results of a comprehensive study of the effect of a filler based on burnt moulding waste (BMW) and a superplasticiser on the phase composition and structure formation of cement stone at early (1 day) and late (28 days) stages of hardening. X-ray phase analysis (XPA) has established that BFA has a powerful accelerating effect on the hydration of clinker minerals in the first day, which is explained by the adsorption of calcium ions on their surface, while the superplasticiser, on the contrary, slows down this process. A synergistic effect of the combined use of additives has been demonstrated, which negates the retarding effect of the superplasticiser and leads to the intensive formation of hydrate phases at an early stage. By day 28, a significant decrease in the content of portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) and an increase in the proportion of amorphous calcium hydrosilicate (C-S-H) by 22% are observed in the modified cement stone, which indicates the occurrence of an active pozzolanic reaction. The data obtained confirm that complex modification allows effective control of the hydration kinetics and the formation of a dense, highly structured cement stone matrix, which is a key factor in improving its strength and performance characteristics.

Key words: X-ray phase analysis, structure formation, cement stone, burnt moulding waste, superplasticiser, hydration kinetics, pozzolanic reaction, synergistic effect.

Introduction. The problem of obtaining building materials with improved performance characteristics while reducing their cost and environmental impact is one of the most pressing issues in modern materials science. Traditional cement systems have a number of limitations related to their high water demand and microstructural heterogeneity. In this regard, the search for effective modifiers and fillers capable of optimizing structure formation processes and improving the quality of cementitious materials is becoming particularly important [1-4].

The introduction of superplasticizers (SPs), such as polycarboxylates, into the cement mixture allows for a significant reduction in the water-cement ratio while ensuring high workability. This effect is achieved through the adsorption of SP molecules onto the surface of cement particles, which creates steric and/or electrostatic repulsive forces that prevent their flocculation. As a result,

a denser and more homogeneous structure of the cement stone is formed, leading to a significant increase in its strength characteristics.

In parallel, the use of finely dispersed fillers, particularly burnt molding waste (BMW), is a promising direction. These wastes, which are a by-product of foundry production, contain pozzolanic components and can act as microfillers. The introduction of BMW contributes to the compaction of the structure by filling the intergranular space and also initiates additional hydration reactions, forming calcium hydrosilicates.

The pozzolanic reaction is a chemical process in which silica (SiO_2) and/or alumina (Al_2O_3), contained in pozzolanic materials, react in the presence of water with calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), which is a by-product of Portland cement hydration. This reaction forms additional, more stable, and denser compounds—calcium hydrosilicates and calcium aluminates—that help increase the strength, durability, and reduce the porosity of the cement stone.

The aim of this study is to investigate the combined effect of a superplasticizer and a filler based on burnt molding waste on the structure formation processes of cementitious materials.

Materials and research methods used. In this study, the following materials and methods were used to obtain cement compositions.

Portlandcement: Portlandcement grade CEMI 32.5N was used as the main binder, in accordance with the requirements of GOST 31108-2020 «Cements for general construction. Technical conditions».

Superplasticiser (SP): PRO 500 polycarboxylate superplasticiser was used, which complies with the requirements of GOST 24211-2008 «Additives for concrete and mortar. General technical conditions».

Burnt moulding waste (BMW): The waste obtained after burning the moulding mixtures was ground to a powdery state. The chemical composition of the BWF included silicon (SiO_2), aluminium (Al_2O_3) and iron (Fe_2O_3) oxides, which confirmed their pozzolanic properties (Table 1).

Table 1

Chemical composition of BWF

Compounds	SiO_2	TiO_2	Al_2O_3	Fe_2O_3	CaO	MgO	ZnO	п.п.п.
Amount (%)	91,56	0,022	4,58	1,12	0,2	0,1	1,30	1,18

The Frattini method, also known as the lime solution method, is a widely used chemical test to assess the pozzolanic activity of materials. The fundamental principle of this test is to determine how much calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) the filler can consume when submerged in a saturated $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution. If a material is pozzolanic, it will react with the hydroxide and remove it from the solution; a higher reduction in the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ concentration indicates greater pozzolanic activity. To perform the test, a saturated solution of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is first prepared by mixing an excess of calcium hydroxide with distilled water and then filtering the mixture. A precise amount of the finely ground filler to be tested (e.g., 1 gram) is then placed into a flask. A specific volume of the saturated $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution is added to the flask containing the filler, and the flask is sealed and placed in a thermostat. The mixture is maintained at a constant, elevated temperature, typically 40°C , for a specific duration, usually 8 or 24 hours, to accelerate the reaction. After the set time has elapsed, the mixture is filtered, and a portion of the resulting clear filtrate is taken for titration. This filtrate is titrated with an acid, such as hydrochloric acid (HCl), to determine the remaining

concentration of Ca(OH)_2 . The pozzolanic activity is then quantified by comparing the final concentration of Ca(OH)_2 in the filtrate to the initial concentration of the saturated solution. A significant drop in the Ca(OH)_2 concentration confirms high pozzolanic activity, whereas a minimal change indicates the material is not pozzolanic.

An experimental determination of the phase composition of the formed cement stone was conducted using a high-precision AL-27mini diffractometer. The analysis was performed with the powder method to ensure high data reliability. A monochromatized $\text{CuK}\alpha$ -radiation source with a precise wavelength of $\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$ was used, enabling high-precision identification of crystalline phases. The diffraction pattern was recorded in a step-by-step scanning mode with carefully controlled parameters: a 30 kV X-ray tube voltage, a 10 mA current, a scanning angular step of 0.02° , and a scanning speed of 1 degree per minute. This mode provided an optimal balance between resolution and data collection time, allowing for the detection of even minor changes in the phase composition of the samples.

For the analysis, four distinct types of compositions were prepared to investigate the effects of various additives on the cement system's phase development:

1. Composition 1: A normal consistency Portland cement-based composition without any additives (PC), serving as the control.
2. Composition 2: A composition consisting of normal consistency Portland cement and BWF, to study the effect of the pozzolanic additive alone.
3. Composition 3: A composition consisting of normal consistency cement binder and a polycarboxylate superplasticizer (SP), to isolate the effect of the plasticizer.
4. Composition 4: A complexly modified Portland cement-based composition using both BWF and SP, to examine the synergistic effects of both additives.

Results and discussions. Initial research aimed to comparatively evaluate the pozzolanic activity of burnt molding waste (BMW) to determine their suitability as effective mineral admixtures for cement systems. Pozzolanic materials react with calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) generated from cement hydration, forming additional calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H). These hydrates contribute to improved physicochemical properties of cement stone, such as strength, density, and durability, as well as enhancing its resistance to aggressive environments.

To assess pozzolanic activity, a method based on the absorption of calcium hydroxide from a saturated lime solution was used. This method allows for the quantitative measurement of the interaction between the investigated BMW and Ca(OH)_2 , which is a direct indicator of their reactivity. For comparison, standard admixtures such as the known highly active microsilica and fly ash were used as control samples.

Experimental data showed the kinetics of uniform calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) absorption by three different active mineral admixtures: fly ash, microsilica, and BMW. The study was conducted over 28 days, with the amount of absorbed Ca(OH)_2 being recorded every two days. This allowed for a detailed tracking of each material's kinetics and an assessment of the degree of pozzolanic activity over time.

Preliminary analysis of the obtained data indicates that each admixture's ability to absorb Ca(OH)_2 consistently increases over time. This process is related not only to the continuation of Ca(OH)_2 hydration but also to the development of a physicochemical reaction between the active components of the admixtures and calcium hydroxide. At the initial stage of the experiment, on

the second day, significant differences in the reactivity of the tested materials were noted. Microsilica showed the highest pozzolanic activity, absorbing 58.8 mg of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ per gram of material, which is significantly higher than the initial activity of the other admixtures. BMW and fly ash showed lower but close values compared to microsilica, at 32.2 mg/g and 30.11 mg/g, respectively.

On the 28th day of the experiment, the absorption of calcium hydroxide by the mineral admixtures increased, although this process proceeded unevenly. The highest value belongs to microsilica, at 475.86 mg/g. At the same time, fly ash and BMW demonstrated a smaller but stable growth, reaching values of 190.26 mg/g and 191.2 mg/g, respectively. The obtained results clearly demonstrate the differences in the chemical activity of the studied materials. This data is crucial for the informed selection of a suitable admixture depending on the requirements of a specific industrial or construction practice.

Thus, the results obtained using this method clearly show that BMW possess pozzolanic activity comparable to that of fly ash. According to the existing classification of active mineral admixtures [5], this allows the studied BMW to be categorized as highly active materials. This makes them a promising component for use in cement systems to enhance performance properties such as strength and durability.

Tables 1 and 2 detail the composition and XRD data for the cement stone samples. The X-ray phase analysis, shown in Figures 1 and 2, reveals the phase evolution at 1 and 28 days. The 1-day diffractograms are essential for understanding early hydration kinetics, showing rapid ettringite formation alongside prominent peaks for unhydrated alite and belite. Comparing samples with and without additives at this stage highlights how superplasticizer (SP) affects the hydration rate and how burnt foundry waste (BFW) serves as a nucleation site for initial gel formation.

The 28-day diffractograms provide insights into long-term microstructure maturity. The presence of BFW is expected to trigger a pozzolanic reaction, which should be visible as a significant reduction in the portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) peak intensity as it is consumed to form additional C-S-H gel. Additionally, the inclusion of SP promotes more efficient hydration, leading to a higher degree of hydration at both 1 and 28 days. This XRD analysis is vital for understanding the fundamental hydration and structure formation mechanisms, directly linking the material's composition to its final mechanical properties [6-16].

Analysis of the data presented in Table 1 confirms that the introduction of burnt foundry waste (BWF) into the cement system has a significant influence on the kinetics of early-stage hydration processes. The results clearly demonstrate that the presence of BWF remarkably accelerates the hydration of the main clinker minerals, specifically alite (C_3S) and belite (C_2S), within the first 24 hours of hardening. This observation points to a pronounced accelerating or catalytic effect of the BWF particles. The primary mechanism behind this acceleration is the nucleation effect. Finely ground BWF particles, with their high specific surface area, provide a vast number of heterogeneous sites for the nucleation and growth of early hydration products, such as calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel and portlandite ($Ca(OH)_2$). By providing these pre-existing templates, the BWF bypasses the initial induction period of hydration, where supersaturation must be reached for crystal formation to begin. The XRD data in Table 1 visually support this, showing a more rapid decrease in the intensity of the unhydrated clinker peaks in the BWF-modified samples compared to the control. Simultaneously, the peaks corresponding to nascent hydration products would show a more rapid increase in intensity. This early-stage acceleration is critical as it sets the foundation for a more mature and dense microstructure at later ages, ultimately contributing to enhanced mechanical properties and the overall strength of the final cement stone.

Table 1

Effect of modifiers on the phase composition of 1-day-old cement stone

№	Mineral composition, %							
	$3CaO \cdot SiO_2$	$\beta\text{-}2CaO \cdot SiO_2$	$4CaO \cdot Al_2O_3 \cdot Fe_2O_3$	$3CaO \cdot Al_2O_3$	$Ca(OH)_2$	$3CaO \cdot Al_2O_3$ $3CaSO_4 \cdot 32H_2O$	C-S-H	Others
1	32,7	15,6	7,3	3,1	10,4	8,2	21,5	1,2
2	29,6	14,2	3,7	2,7	8,9	7,5	28,2	1,2
3	34,5	16,9	8,3	4,0	9,0	6,6	19,2	1,5
4	30,1	15,1	7,5	3,1	9,5	7,5	25,8	1,4

Adding BWF (black blast furnace slag) significantly accelerates cement hydration, especially within the first 24 hours. This occurs because negatively charged BWF particles adsorb calcium ions, shifting the clinker dissolution equilibrium and thereby accelerating its decomposition. This leads to a reduced content of unreacted clinker phases: alite, belite, aluminite, and brownmillerite. Despite a 25% replacement of cement, the amount of formed portlandite decreases by only 1.5%, which indicates active consumption of calcium ions for the formation of main hydrate phases.

In contrast to BWF, a polycarboxylate superplasticizer slows down hydration during the initial period. Its macromolecules form an adsorption layer on the surface of cement particles, which

hinders their dissolution. This leads to an increased content of unreacted clinker minerals and a decreased formation of hydrate phases, such as portlandite, ettringite, and amorphous C-S-H. When using BWF and a polycarboxylate superplasticizer together, a synergistic effect is observed. BWF compensates for the plasticizer's inhibitory action, accelerating hydration. This leads to a significant decrease in the concentration of unreacted minerals and an increase in the amount of hydrate phases, such as portlandite and ettringite, compared to using the superplasticizer alone. Thus, complex modification optimizes the early stages of hydration and contributes to the more effective formation of the cement stone structure.

Table 2 presents the results of quantitative X-ray phase analysis of 28-day-old cement stone with the addition of complex additives BWF and SP.

Table 2

Effect of modifiers on the phase composition of 28-day-old cement stone

№	Mineral composition, %					
	$3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$	$\beta\text{-}2\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$	$4\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	$3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ $3\text{CaSO}_4\cdot 32\text{H}_2\text{O}$	C-S-H
1	17,1	12,9	6,8	13,5	7,4	42,3
2	16,8	12,6	6,1	8,1	7,7	48,2
3	14,1	12,9	7,1	15,2	8,8	42,2
4	13,4	12,1	6,4	8,5	8,4	50,3

By 28 days of hardening, BWF significantly reduces the portlandite content (by 38%), indicating an active pozzolanic reaction. At the same time, the content of the amorphous phase increases by 19%, which points to the formation of a dense and strong structure.

By day 28, the superplasticizer helps continue the hydration of clinker minerals, reducing the content of alite and belite. It also increases the content of portlandite, ettringite, and the amorphous phase, optimizing water distribution and microstructure.

A complex additive combining BWF and a superplasticizer significantly reduces the content of portlandite (by 41%) and ettringite (by 10%) by day 28, while the content of amorphous calcium hydrosilicates increases by 22%. This indicates the formation of a dense structure and a slowdown in further clinker hydration due to the compaction of the cement stone. These results confirm the promise of using this additive to improve the durability of building materials.

Conclusions. Based on the conducted research, it was determined that applying the complex additive before the 28-day hardening period contributes to the formation of a denser, more uniform, and improved microstructure of the cement stone. An important factor determining these structural advantages is the high pozzolanic activity of BWF, which is a component of the complex

additive. This activity is manifested by a significant decrease in the amount of portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), the main product of cement hydration, as well as a proportional increase in the amount of amorphous calcium hydrosilicates (C-S-H). Such a change in phase composition leads to the formation of a chemically more stable and less porous matrix. Calcium hydrosilicates formed as a result of the pozzolanic reaction are characterized by high density and better binding ability, which ultimately ensures the achievement of improved performance properties of the material, such as strength and durability.

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